

Definition of a guide of best practices in the creation and updating of Knowledge Graphs from scientific literature on coronaviruses and creation of a data actualization pipeline for Drugs4Covid.

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1. Abstract

Knowledge Graphs have proven to be a valuable resource for presenting the information extracted from document collections. There are tools and methodologies that partially cover each of the steps required in the knowledge graph construction process. However, the description of the general flow is usually overlooked in the works that follow this process to construct knowledge graphs. Static processes are normally used for building them, but when the collection varies over time, an approach that facilitates incremental processing of the data is required.

In this work, we propose a set of best practices and a workflow to create periodically updated knowledge graphs from evolving corpora. In order to evaluate the usability of our approach, a full process has been implemented in the context of the Drugs4Covid¹ project. The aim of this process is to create a knowledge graph based on the biomedical entities extracted from the scientific publications collected in the CORD-19² dataset. It was found that the modularity of the guidelines, in terms of the steps to be followed, facilitates the customization and adaptability of the entire procedure.

¹ <https://drugs4covid.oeg.fi.upm.es>

² <https://allenai.org/data/cord-19>

2. Introduction

Knowledge graphs [1] (KGs) are digital structures that represent knowledge as entities and the relationships between them. By using KGs, data is structured and can be more accessible for both humans and machines in a way that inferences can be established between concepts and even new knowledge can also be generated. KGs are a versatile resource used in many contexts, which includes research in scientific areas. Constructing KGs from scientific literature enables to explore the scientific information published each year more effectively, since they are used for both information retrieval (IR) [2] and information extraction (IE) tasks.

During the covid-19 pandemic, there was a steep surge in the number of publications regarding the SARS-CoV2 virus [3]. This situation over time led to a high amount of coronavirus related scientific literature, which was too high for a manual review by the scientific community. For this reason, a multitude of KG were constructed to condense the information on covid-19 and relate it to information already available in public databases or other resources [4]. These KG were essential in IE and IR tasks [4], but among the different IE tasks, drug repurposing stood out to be the objective of almost half of the KGs constructed from covid-19 related scientific literature. This makes sense since these KGs were constructed in a context where there was a low availability of treatments and drugs to fight covid-19 and a high number of publications regarding this disease.

The main problem with the KGs created during the pandemic is that most are static, meaning that they represent the knowledge contained in a given corpus at a given time. However, as the covid-19 corpus is ever-increasing and evolving, it is necessary to update these KGs to include the latest findings and make the knowledge available.

A methodology has been proposed to ease the KG construction process [5]. It includes all steps of the construction process, from the collection of publications to the generation of the KG. Although this methodology covers the whole process, it serves the purpose of structuring in great detail the work described in each article. It is a domain-independent method to extract the processes, methods and materials used to conduct the work described in the article. This means that the entities and relations specific to scientific methods are not extracted as such. Another system that partially addresses the topic of this study is the iTextMine tool [6]³. iTextMine integrates text mining and relation extraction tools from the title and abstracts of scientific articles published in PubMed⁴. The results are presented as a KG with entities and their relations. Moreover, this system provides a REST API⁵ for an easy programming interface. Although this system addresses the problem of the study, it only recognizes the entities and relations present in the abstract and title of the publications, missing out on the information contained in the body of the article. This study was the only work found to cover the research topic of this study and many tools and methodologies have been developed to deal with different steps of the construction process. For example, PubTator Central⁶ (PTC) [7] is a Web-based system used to extract some biomedical entities in PubMed abstracts and PMC full-text articles, or any text by using the integrated API

³ <https://research.bioinformatics.udel.edu/itextmine/integrate>

⁴ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁵ <https://restfulapi.net/>

⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/research/pubtator/>

service. However, these entities are not condensed into a knowledge graph. SemRep⁷ is a program that extracts subject-relation-object triplets from texts, extracting both biomedical entities and the relationships between them. KGs are usually created to fit a domain and a point in time, however, there are scenarios that require more flexibility to cover a flow of information that evolves over time. In these cases, KGs should evolve at the same time as the flow of information they cover.

Hypothesis and objectives:

This work was conducted with the hypothesis that guidelines to automate the construction of updating knowledge graphs can be defined and implemented to offer the knowledge about COVID-19 retrieved from scientific literature. With this hypothesis in mind, several objectives were defined, (1) demonstrate the need for such guidelines; (2) define the guide in a way that it can be easily understood and applicable; and (3) implement the guide to publish the knowledge generated in the Drugs4Covid project.

In order to reach the proposed objectives, the methodology followed in this work consisted first in conducting a systematic literature review (SLR) of the different KGs that have been generated from scientific publications in the case of covid-19 literature. This review was done with the objective in mind that the different methods used could be understood and considered for the proposed guidelines, as well as to ensure that there is no methodology followed that is being applied to do this process. Then, based on the SLR result and analyzing the KGs construction processes followed in other developments, a guide of best practices was defined. Finally, the guidelines have been implemented in the case of the Drugs4Covid project.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Systematic literature review

A systematic literature review was conducted following the methodology described in [8]. First, a search of articles on the subject area was done in PubMed, Web of Science and Scopus, for this a set of inclusion criteria were used to include the articles in the study. The articles were downloaded and filtered. Filtering was done by removing duplicates and by a manual reading of the titles and abstracts in order to discard articles out of the scope of this review, among other exclusion criteria defined. Fig.1 shows an overview of the article selection and filtering process.

Then, in order to compare and analyze the texts retrieved, a set of features were defined and extracted from each document in a way that the texts could be described by them. The different steps are explained in more detail below.

3.1.1. Articles Search

For the searches, the following five criteria were considered:

⁷ https://lhncbc.nlm.nih.gov/ii/tools/SemRep_SemMedDB_SKR/SemRep.html

- IC1: Text in English or Spanish.
- IC2: “COVID” related terms appear in either title or abstract.
- IC3: Published between 2019 and 2022.
- IC4: “Knowledge Graph” related terms appear in either title or abstract.
- IC5: Text classified in the source as belonging to any biomedical/computational biology/computer science fields.

These inclusion criteria were transformed into search queries that could be queried in the specified repositories. The queries used to get the documents along with the source are shown in Table 1.

Metadata of the documents returned in the search, such as title, doi, authors, venue, etc, was downloaded as csv files from all the articles. A total of 218 documents were retrieved.

Fig. 1 Overview of the article selection and filtering process.

Then, the articles were automatically reviewed for duplicates either in the title or in the DOI through an R script. Duplicated articles were removed so 205 documents were left for further studying.

3.1.2. Selection Criteria

Next, the collection of 205 documents was refined by defining the following exclusion criteria to discard documents:

- EC1: Out of the research scope of this review by manual screening of abstracts and titles. For this exclusion criteria, each abstract and title were subject of a manual reading and the document was excluded if there were no indications of the construction of a knowledge graph using covid related information from publications. By using this criterion, relevant articles could have been excluded, as some articles may not mention their methods in the abstract.
- EC2: No peer-to-peer reviews (from BioRxiv and MedRxiv).
- EC3: Resources not freely accessible.

By following these criteria, from the 205 documents, only 14 texts were selected and subject of a narrower reading. Although selected, the articles could still be out of the scope of this review due to low information provided about the methodology.

Source	Search Query	Number of results	Date of query
PubMed	((corpus covid knowledge graph[Title/Abstract]) OR (corpus coronavirus knowledge graph[Title/Abstract])) OR (corpus COVID-19 knowledge graph[Title/Abstract])	5	27/1/2022
PubMed	(((((extraction covid data[Title/Abstract]) OR (extraction coronavirus data[Title/Abstract])) OR (extraction COVID-19 data[Title/Abstract])) OR (extracting covid data[Title/Abstract])) OR (extracting coronavirus data[Title/Abstract])) OR (extracting COVID-19 data[Title/Abstract]) Filters: Free full text, English, Spanish, from 2019 - 2022/1/27	88	27/1/2022
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid AND knowledge AND graph) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid AND knowledge AND graph) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid-19 AND knowledge AND graph) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (coronavirus AND knowledge AND graph)) AND (EXCLUDE (OA , "all")) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NURS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "SOCI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "VETE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ENER") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CHEM") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "BUSI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "EART") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ECON") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PSYC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ARTS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "DENT")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "Spanish"))	90	27/1/2022
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid AND corpus AND knowledge AND graph) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (coronavirus AND corpus AND knowledge AND graph) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid-19 AND corpus AND knowledge AND graph) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ARTS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "ENER") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "SOCI"))	11	27/1/2022
Web of Science	((((TI=(knowledge graph covid)) OR AB=(knowledge graph covid)) OR ((TI=(KG covid)) OR AB=(KG covid))) OR ((TI=(knowledge graph coronavirus)) OR AB=(knowledge graph coronavirus)) OR ((TI=(KG coronavirus)) OR AB=(KG coronavirus))) OR ((TI=(knowledge graph SARS-cov)) OR AB=(knowledge graph SARS-cov)) OR ((TI=(KG SARS-cov)) OR AB=(KG SARS-cov))) Filters: Open access, english or spanish, computer science field, from 2019	24	09/02/2022

Table 1 Queries and number of results obtained in each search

3.1.3. Feature extraction

In order to compare the different texts, we need to define a set of features to describe the content of articles. For this, a series of research questions were proposed, and features were defined as answers to these questions in each document. The research questions proposed are listed below.

1. What are use cases of the covid-19 KGs?
2. What is the availability of the resources used to construct covid-19 KGs?
3. What are the sources of data for covid-19 KGs?
4. To what databases the covid-19 KGs link their information?

5. What part of the methodology followed to construct covid-19 KGs is mentioned?
6. What format do the covid-19 KGs use for the data?

The features defined were used to compare the texts and analyze the methods used to construct covid-19 KG. A total of 50 features were defined to compare the texts and are available at Table 1 of the supplementary material.

3.2. Materials for the implementation.

In this work, a guide has been developed to deal with the problem of constructing updating-KGs from evolving scientific literature sources. This guide was defined using diagrams.net (previously draw.io)⁸, a widely used diagramming software. The definition of the guide included defining a legend to represent each element required in the process, this legend is shown on Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Legend designed for the created guidelines

Next, the guidelines were applied in the particular context of Drugs4Covid. For this implementation, a series of resources and methods were adapted to fit the proposed workflow.

The workflow is implemented with the Apache-Nifi software⁹. It is a software developed by the Apache Software Foundation used for the flow of data automation between different softwares. It can be used both from the command line and with an integrated User Interface (UI) to design the flow. Among its features, it can integrate in the flow scripts written in programming languages other than Java. It allows for a high degree of control of the different

⁸ <https://www.diagrams.net/>

⁹ <https://nifi.apache.org/>

paths the files can take. This high degree of control is possible because each processor can route for success, failure, and many different execution result possibilities, which can be in turn routed to different execution paths.

As for the document database, the Apache SOLR¹⁰ database was selected, in part because it was the database used to store the documents in the project, but also because it is also compatible with the Apache-Nifi flow automation tool. Moreover, both Apache-Nifi and SOLR are open source.

As for the choice of scripting programming languages, python was selected for the tasks for which a native Nifi processor was not defined nor found, or for other tasks that could be written as scripts. Some of the most important libraries and modules used in this work are: pysolr to retrieve/put documents from/to the SOLR repository, json to work with json files, fastapi to create the Applied Programming Interfaces (API) services needed.

APIs are a type of software interface that connects two softwares. This guide defines 3 APIs to use in the proposed workflow, and the APIs designed take an input, process the input and return the processed information.

CORD-19: CORD-19 [9] is a large corpus of scientific publications regarding the SARS-COV2 virus. It started in 2020 with a collection of approximately 28K publications, and has been updated periodically, containing now more than 200K publications.

Bio-NER: For the information extraction step, 3 specific trained models to identify drugs, diseases and genes are used and taken from the Bio-NER¹¹ service. Bio-NER service is a service to

Java Script Object Notation or JSON¹² [10] is a data-interchange format that shares conventions with many popular programming languages such as Java or python. It is easy for both humans and machines to write, parse and analyze. It consists of key-value pairs that can contain different types of information, and arrays to hold a group of values.

Another data format used in this work is the Resource Description Format (RDF)¹³, used in the semantic web. It consists of information in triples, with a subject, relation, object, each of them corresponding to a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI).

For the data semantification, the Evidences and Provenance of Associations Between Concepts¹⁴ (EBOCA) ontology was considered. The ontology, shown on Fig.3, is used to describe evidences of associations between concepts. In this work, it has been modified to allow for the description of associations between the 3 biomedical entities studied, being Genes, Chemicals and Diseases. To this end, 3 different classes of the "Association" class were introduced; each connected by the object property "refersTo" to the biomedical concepts that they associate. Moreover, the 3 biomedical entities studied have been added

¹⁰ <https://solr.apache.org/>

¹¹ <https://library.github.io/bio-ner/>

¹² <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

¹³ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

¹⁴ <https://Drugs4Covid.github.io/EBOCA-portal>

as classes as well. Each association individual refers to the biomedical concepts associated, in the sense that a gene-disease association refers to a Gene and a Disease.

Fig. 3. Extract of evidences from the EBOCA ontology

Mapeathor: Mapeathor¹⁵ [11], a system to transform rules written in a spreadsheet into the desired mapping language. In our case, rules are transformed into the RDF Mapping Language (RML) [12]. The output of this system is a mapping file written in the specified mapping language to be used in a mapping engine. This system was used to produce the mapping file of the EBOCA ontology for the creation of the semantification API. This was done by checking the JSON fields that were of interest and writing the necessary transformation as mapping rules in the spreadsheet.

¹⁵ <https://morph.oeg.fi.upm.es/tool/mapeathor>

Morph-KGC¹⁶ [13] is a tool to construct KGs using a mapping file in RML and data in JSON format among many supported formats. It is used in the implementation to generate the RDF information to publish in the graph database.

GraphDB¹⁷ is a graph database from ontotext that can be accessed through an API to publish new information into a KG.

Supplementary material as well as scripts and other resources are available at: <https://github.com/drugs4covid/knowledge-acquisition>.

4. Results

4.1. SLR results.

We first present the document information of each text. It consists of the venue type, name and ranking (if applicable), the year published and the text availability.

Among the 14 scientific articles obtained after the systematic review described in Section 3.1, 7 come from journals and 7 come from conferences, and the only repeated venue is Bioinformatics, in 3 articles. The quality measure for 4 conferences was not possible to assign, but the rest of the texts (10/14) come from venues either with a CORE ranking¹⁸ B or above, or with an impact factor¹⁹ Q2 or Q1.

While 3 articles were published in 2020, the rest were published in 2021. All 14 texts were accessible since this was an exclusion factor, however it should be noted that 2 texts were only accessible through the UPM institution.

Next, we studied the different use cases that the covid knowledge graph could have. Here, use cases can be divided on Information Extraction (IE) or Information Retrieval (IR) tasks. Among the 14 texts, 10/14 covid KGs have as the main use case IE tasks and 4/14 have as the main use case IR tasks. The different IE tasks identified for covid-19 KG are drug repurposing (6/14), question answering (1/14), association rule mining (1/14) and covid concepts taxonomization (1/14). IR tasks could not be further specified.

The availability of the resources presented in the texts was assessed. These resources are the data used as input, the code used in the work and the KG constructed. The KG is explicitly mentioned to be available in 4/14 texts, the code is explicitly mentioned to be available in 7/14 texts, and the data or code to produce the data is available in 8/14 texts. Moreover, all 3 resources are jointly available in 3/14 texts and no resource is available or was not found to be available in 5/14 texts.

Concerning the data used to construct the KG, the different sources of input documents were identified and compared between texts. 12/14 articles use unstructured covid data as input, while 8/14 used structured data in the form of KGs, structured datasets or RDF

¹⁶ <https://morph.oeg.fi.upm.es/tool/morph-kgc>

¹⁷ <https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/>

¹⁸ <https://www.core.edu.au/conference-portal>

¹⁹ <https://www.scimagojr.com/>

datasets. Structured data was used to extend the knowledge extracted from publications or integrate that knowledge with other KGs.

The sources for input covid publication data are: CORD-19 [9] corpus 7/14, Pubmed 2/14, LitCovid 2/14, Targeting2019-nCoV (by GHDDI) 1/14, University of Luxembourg Covid corpus 1/14 and EuropePMC 1/14. Moreover, some unstructured data sources that do not contain covid-19 publications were also considered, these include clinical trials from clinicaltrials.org 2/14, patents from the LENS dataset 1/14, encyclopedic articles from Baidu Encyclopedia 1/14, covid-related concepts from the IATE (Interactive Terminology for Europe) 1/14, chemical information from the Cas content collection 1/14 and SemMed annotations from the SemMedDB 1/14.

In some articles, the data collected is then linked to other existing databases, however there is not a consensus on what databases to link. The most linked to databases are Uniprot, Gene Ontology, STRINGDB and DrugBank, each being linked to in 2/14 KGs. Other linked to databases include IntAct, Protein Ontology, GTex, iPTMnet, CoV-AbDab, PharmGKB, Therapeutic Target Database, ChEMBL, Cellmap and PathwayCommons, each being linked to in 1/14 KG. However 8/14 KGs did not link the data to any other database or at least did not mention to do so in the texts.

Next the methodology followed to construct the Knowledge graph and to conduct the work was assessed. The methodology to build the KG was mentioned in 8/14, not detailed enough in 3/14 and not found in 3/14 texts. Moreover, the methods used for information extraction from the texts are mentioned in 9/14 articles, however they are not described in a way that could be reproducible or reused in another work in most of the articles.

When mentioned, the methods to extract information from the covid-19 literature include SemRep 2/14, manual codification into Biological Expression Language (BEL) scripts 1/14, iTextMine 1/14, PubTator 1/14, a BioBERT-based information extraction pipeline 1/14, DBpedia Spotlight 1/14, FastText word embedding (WE) 1/14 and NCBO BioPortal Annotator 1/14.

Finally, the KG data was assessed in terms of the format used to represent the KG, the storage of KG and data query language. The format of the KG was found to be mentioned on 5/14 articles, and the formats used to store KGs are KGX and GraphML for 2/14 KG and SIF, text/turtle format and NDEX for 1/14 KGs.

KG storage was only found to be mentioned in 9/14 articles, but there seems to be a consensus that Neo4j is the preferred database to store covid-19 KG. 6/14 KGs are stored or can be potentially stored in a Neo4j database, 1/14 in OpenLink Virtuoso, 1/14 in MongoDB and 1/14 in OrientDB.

As for the query language, all 6/14 Neo4j use cypher as the query language, but other query languages are used such as Corese, MGExplorer, RESTful API and SPARQL endpoint (all in 1/14 KG).

4.2 Guide definition

Through the SLR conducted, different methods and characteristics required to construct KGs from scientific publications were reported, however the processes were mostly poorly described. To combat this problem, the processes were outlined and ordered in order to extract different steps and to generalize the methods used.

Then, all the information collected was harmonized into the proposed guidelines, divided on 5 steps, each of them responsible for a specific transformation of the data. An overview of the guidelines is presented in Fig.4. In the following subsections, each step will be described in more detail.

Fig.4 Overview of the steps followed by the guidelines developed in this work.

4.2.1 Harvesting

This step, depicted on Fig.5, is responsible for the collection of the data from the source of scientific publications. Moreover, the new data is detected and ingested and the removed data should also be removed from the KG.

First, the identification of the source(s) of scientific publications is provided by the user as the URL of the corpus/corpora. If only a fraction of the corpus is used, belonging to a given domain for example, a filtering query should be provided by the user. The query would be composed of terms that match the theme of interest.

Fig. 5. Detailed data harvesting step

Once the source has been set, the next step is to get from the source a list of potential publications to process. This initial list may include documents already processed and documents to be processed as it is directly retrieved from the source of publications.

If the guidelines are followed for the first time and no document database has been previously set up to store the information, then the list of potential publications only includes new publications to process. However, if there is already a document database set up, a process begins to retrieve from it a list of all the already processed publications. Then begins the process of incremental detection. This process consists of checking what publication ids are on the source list that are not on the document database (ids of publications to process), and what publication ids are on the document database but not on the source list (ids of retrieved, moved, or deleted publications from the source). If an update to the source has been detected, the date of the last update is stored in a file to be later used in the construction guidelines. From this process, two lists of publications are produced, one containing the publications to process and add to the knowledge graph, and another containing publications already processed to be removed or modified according to their removal from the source database. If the list of publications to remove from the document database is not empty, a process begins to remove these publications from the document database, since they have been retrieved from the source.

Finally, the publications to be processed are downloaded from the provided source in the format available, but preferably PDF and with the text body available. It should be noted that if the publications from the source are already pre-processed and parsed to a JSON format, the following step of pre-processing is not necessary.

4.2.2 Pre-processing

In this step, shown on Fig. 6, the raw unstructured publications are transformed to the JSON format, in order to be more easily processed in the following steps.

A service API can be developed that takes as input an unstructured publication and returns a JSON with all the information contained in the publication. A detailed description of the API is provided on Fig.7. Any structured publication in JSON will be directly passed onto the next step of information extraction.

Fig. 6. Detailed pre-processing step

Here, the user should provide the PDF to JSON transformer to use. If the selected PDF to JSON parser already separates the body text among paragraphs, just the parser is needed. However, if this step is not performed, there can be a further transformation of the JSON to separate its body text among paragraphs. This is very important but not mandatory since the guide was conceptualized to extract entities at a paragraph level. If, however, it is desired to break up the document even further at a sentence level, it should also be possible.

Fig. 7 Setup process of the preprocessing API

The output of this step is for each publication in plain text, a reformatted JSON file. The recommended minimal information that it should contain is the abstract, full body text and an identifier for the publication.

4.2.3 Information extraction

In the step depicted in Fig.8, the knowledge contained in each publication is extracted from their text.

The JSON files of each publication generated in the previous step are taken as input.

Each JSON file of the publications is separated into multiple different files. One JSON file containing a unique paper identifier and additional information, which is uploaded to the document database without entity extraction to keep track of the amount of papers processed, and for the incremental detection step. The other JSON files contain each a paragraph of the input JSON paper. Each contains at least a unique paragraph identifier, the paper identifier and the text of the paragraph.

Fig. 8. Detailed information extraction step

Each JSON file of a paragraph is then sent to an API service built with (a) given Named Entity Recognition (NER) model(s) by the user to extract the entities contained in it. Moreover, a relation extraction model could be also integrated in this service in order to take advantage of the most of each publication, but this is optional as it can be enough to only extract the entities.

For the creation of the annotator API, described in Fig. 9, we have 3 possibilities: 1) if the NER model is on the web; 2) if the NER model is part of a library; 3) if there are models on the web AND available as libraries. Although models as libraries are considered and could be usable, it is still preferable and easier to integrate a NER model located on the web as it can be easier to set up an API service to access it. The input of the API would be a JSON file containing at least the text to annotate, and the output is a JSON file with the text and with the entities detected in it and the relations between entities if a relation extraction was provided.

Fig. 9. Detailed diagram showing the set-up process of the Annotator API

Finally, the JSONs containing the entities extracted from the texts are uploaded to the document database and also sent to the next step of the process. This is done because one of the results of the workflow is the document database with the paragraphs annotated so that the user can study both the KG and the document database.

From this step, the document database has been updated with the new information in the JSON format, and these JSON files are sent to the next step for the semantification.

4.2.4 Semantification

This step, shown on Fig. 10, consists of adding meaning to the entities detected in the publications, according to an ontology. The overall process is to convert these entities to RDF so that the data is more readable for both machines and humans, and for the later implementation of the information in a knowledge graph.

The JSON files with the entities extracted in the previous step are taken as input.

This transformation is performed by a rule engine from a Relational Database (RDB) to RDF Mapping Language²⁰ (R2RML). An ontology mapping file is required to fit the entities extracted. Mapping files are files that contain extraction rules to extract the information contained in a structured file such as CSV, JSON or any RDB as triples. These extraction rules need to be defined according to a given ontology. There are different mapping languages in which the mapping file could be written, however R2RML was selected as the

²⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>

most general since it can work with different types of structured data. That said, any mapping language and engine could be used instead of R2RML-dependent ones.

Fig. 10. Detailed semantification step

The mapping file provided acts as a template and should be modified to best fit each JSON. The next step would be to extract the RDF information with the R2RML engine provided. All these steps could be performed through an API service described in Fig. 11 that takes the mapping file and a JSON file with the entities to extract as an input, and outputs a JSON file containing the information in RDF.

From this step, the knowledge extracted in the last step is transformed into a RDF format.

Fig. 11. Detailed diagram showing the set-up process of the Semantificator API

4.2.5 Publication

As shown on Fig. 12, in this step the KG is generated by uploading the RDF information to a triple store in order to make it available and accessible. The extracted RDF data is to be transformed in this step. Optionally, if the selected triple store allows for it, the stored date of actualization of the source can be used in conjunction with the RDF data to construct a named knowledge graph, with the name being its date of update/creation. Ideally, this step would also be conducted through the API of the selected graph database if available. The resulting KG is publicly available and accessible. A full guide is depicted in Fig 13 and all diagrams are available at the supplementary material.

Fig. 12. Detailed publication step

Fig. 13 Complete proposed guidelines for the generation of KG from scientific publications.

4.3. Drugs4Covid case study.

The Drugs4Covid [14] project started at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, in a context of low availability of drugs to fight COVID-19, high hospitalization rates and a high and ever-increasing number of COVID-19-related publications. The problem being that the number of publications regarding COVID-19 is very large and due to this, it is very difficult for scientists to explore. The aim of this project is to process all the new COVID-19-related information contained in each new publication, and to integrate this information with the information on available drugs to be used as replacements to fight COVID-19.

The guidelines are implemented as a use case in the Drugs4Covid project, with the aim to automate the actualization of the KG generated. The workflow is implemented with the Apache-Nifi software. The schematic implementation of the guidelines is represented in Fig.14 below. This project relies on the CORD-19 corpus as the main source of publications. From the review conducted at the beginning of this work, we observed that this corpus is the preferred corpus to study COVID-19 in the context of KG construction. The articles contained in it are already parsed to a JSON format, thus the pre-processing step is not necessary in this use case.

Fig.14 Overview of the guidelines implementation in the context of Drugs4Covid

4.3.1 Harvesting

We start by checking if the CORD-19 has been updated in the month previous to the execution of the guidelines. This is checked by sending a request to the CORD-19 archive for each of the days of the last month and by checking for valid response codes (200). If an update has been detected, the date is checked against the date of the last update, stored in a file or in a database (Graph or document oriented). If no update was detected, the flow is stopped.

If an update was detected, then the compressed directory file "document parses.tar.gz" containing the JSON documents is downloaded from the CORD-19 archive. From this file, the ids of the articles are stored on a list. Simultaneously, the ids of the documents that have been already processed and included in the KG are retrieved from the Drugs4Covid SOLR repository and stored on a list. Then, the 2 lists of publication ids are compared, and 2 lists are produced, one containing the ids of articles to further process and one with the ids of articles that have been retrieved from the corpus. This second list of publication ids is then returned to the SOLR repository in order to change the JSONs adding the date of retrieval from the corpus. On the other hand, the ids of publications to process are used to extract from the zip file all the new publications to keep processing.

4.3.2 Information extraction

For the information extraction step, 3 specific trained models to identify drugs, diseases and genes are used and taken from the Bio-NER service. The JSON articles are separated as stipulated on the guidelines into 2 files, one containing metadata of the article and sent directly to the SOLR repository, and the other sent to the annotation API described below. Paper and paragraph JSON examples are depicted on figures 15 and 16 below.

A script was generated that could extract from the JSON publications only the information necessary for the model. The script consisted in the adaptation of this API service into the Nifi workflow. This way, the JSON publication files could be sent as a request to the API and the response received, if successful, is a JSON file with the entity types detected. This new JSON generated is uploaded to the SOLR repository.

```
id : 8ea4508c5d57dbc2b7c9e664b23784a5d376b356
name_s : Cutaneous adverse reactions from 35,229 doses of Sinovac and AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccination: a prospective cohort study in healthcare workers Letter to the Editor Data availability statement Letter to the Editor Letter to the Editor
url_s : https://api.semanticscholar.org/v1/paper/8ea4508c5d57dbc2b7c9e664b23784a5d376b356
abstract_t : Cutaneous adverse reactions (CARs) from mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccines have been reported in the literature. 1,2 On the contrary, information regarding Sinovac (Corona-Vac), (SV) inactivated virus and adenoviral vector AstraZeneca (ChAdOx1 nCoV-19) (AZ) vaccines remains scarce. We have conducted this prospective cohort study to address this issue. The participants were healthcare workers (persons who deliver services to the patients directly or indirectly 3 ) at King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital, Bangkok, Thailand who agreed to be vaccinated with either SV or AZ COVID-19 vaccines. All participants with CARs were identified from the questionnaire sent out on day 1 and day 7 via mobile phone application, the self-reporting system, incident reports of reactions at the vaccination site, emergency room and Dermatology outpatient clinic. Photographic documentation of the skin lesions was obtained from the patients. These photos were assessed by three dermatologists and the skin findings were categorized. A total of 35 229 injections, 29 907 of SV and 5322 of AZ were given during the study period. The number of cases with CARs was 204 from SV and 36 from AZ (total n = 240). The median (interquartile range (IQR)) age of the cases was 34 (26, 43.5) and 48 (35, 55), from SV and AZ, respectively. A female preponderance was observed (female n = 169 (82.84%) and 27 (75%), SV, AZ). Among 240 cases, there were 302 reactions reported. The number of participants experiencing 1 or more than one CAR from SV was 96.79% and 3.21%, and 97.73% and 2.27% from AZ. The incidence of CARs from SV was 0.94% and 0.70% from the first and second doses, whereas those of AZ were 1% and 0.52%, respectively. Dermatologic findings were categorized only from cases with available clinical photographs (n = 145 reactions (48.01%)). Urticaria was the most common skin finding (n = 104, 34.44%) followed by eczematous reactions (n = 21, 6.95%) and angioedema (n = 9, 2.98%). Details are shown in None. None.
_version_ : 1727449796034166800
```

Fig. 15 Example of paper JSON

```

text_t : . When the first and second doses were analysed, 155 and 33 participants who developed CARs cases from the first doses of SV and AZ, respectively, went on to
receive a second dose of the same vaccine. Skin reactions were found in 50 (32.26%) and 3 (9.09%) cases in these cases after the second dose of SV or AZ. Table
2 provides information on the recurrence. Compared to those who experienced urticaria >30 minutes after the first vaccination, those who experienced a first
reaction within 30 min after the first vaccination had an increased risk of urticaria after the second vaccination (OR 2.9 (95%CI 0.44-19.3); P = 0.27).
id : fa6b0b180ad8857b0b46d0807bdd5ad9
article_id_s : 8ea4508c5d57dbc2b7c9e664b23784a5d376b356
size_l : 627
▼ mesh_codes_ss [1]
  0 : D000080223
▼ cui_codes_ss [5]
  0 : C0578870
  1 : C1304193
  2 : C0263338
  3 : C1304191
  4 : C5197720
▶ diseases_ss [2]
▼ disease_terms_ss [1]
  0 : Chronic Urticaria
▼ disease_types_ss [1]
  0 : Immune system disease|Skin disease
_version_ : 1727449796256465000

```

Fig.16 Example of paragraph JSON

4.3.3 Semantification

In order to add meaning according to the EBOCA ontology to the entities extracted in the last step, first a mapping file was designed with Mapeathor and this file was used to design an API service. This API service contains the mapping file and uses the morph-kgc library in Python to take as input a JSON with the paragraph information along with its entities, and the paper information. The information contained in both JSONs is semantified according to the ontology and a RDF file is outputted with the information contained in these documents.

The relations between the different entities are for now only based on evidence, meaning that they are constructed if both entities are a different type, and they appear in the same paragraph. In future work, a relation extraction model could be implemented to further extend the utility of the findings reported.

4.3.4 Publication

Finally, as for the choice of a triple store, it was decided to use Graph DB, however Virtuoso or Neo4j could be also considered. Each RDF file generated at the same date, will be jointly sent to a Graph DB repository so that all the information added on a given day is collected into a named knowledge graph, named after the date of the execution of this workflow. The resulting KG will be publicly available and accessible.

5. Discussion

Regarding the related work, the construction of covid-19 related KGs is an active field of research since there was a 366% increase in the number of publications covering this topic published between 2020 and 2021. Most articles (71.42%) are published in high quality venues (Q1 or Q2 and CORE ranking A or B conferences), showing that this field of research is important to the scientific community. IE tasks are the most prominent use cases (in 71.42% of the KG studied) amongst the different covid-19 KG studied in this work. These tasks are useful to extract information from the literature and use that information to advance in the research on covid-19. The majority of the KGs studied here are created to repurpose

drugs to fight covid-19 (in 42.85% of the covid-19 KG studied here), as the process of the development and validation of a new drug usually takes a considerable amount of time and repurposing a currently existing drug can provide access to drugs to fight covid-19 until specific drugs can be developed if still needed.

Although not as present as IE tasks (71.42% vs 28.58%), IR tasks are still crucial and very studied. They help the researchers navigate the high amount of covid-19 articles and filter the articles most interesting according to a search query. This considerably reduces the time dedicated to search the literature and accelerates the research on covid-19. Regarding resource availability, it was a surprise to see that most works on covid-19 KG did not make their resources publicly available or make only a part of them available. Moreover, only 21.43% of the articles studied provide free access to their related resources (data, code and KG) and 35.71% of them did not make available any resource.

The COVID-19 corpus has been used as input publication data in 50% of the KGs studied. This is the most widely used covid corpus to make covid KGs, as other publication sources such as Pubmed or LitCovid are only used as input in 14.28% of the KGs each. Targeting2019-nCoV (by GHDDI), University of Luxembourg Covid corpus and EuropePMC are also used to get covid-19 documents, but they are only used in 7.14% of the KGs studied each. Regarding the connections to other sources of data, it was found that in 64.28% of the KGs studied, no link was established to external structured databases or at least no link was mentioned in the texts. The rest of the KGs are linked to some databases, however there is no common database between all KGs, in fact, the most linked to database is linked in 14.28% of the KGs. Among these KGs, 21.42% are highly linked with connections to at least 5 external databases, while 14.28% are connected to 1 or 2 external databases and the rest remain with no connections. This is a point of improvement for later covid-19 KGs.

The methodologies used to extract information from articles are mentioned in 64.28% of the works studied here, however no method was used extensively, as SemRep, a rule-based semantic interpreter, is the only tool used in more than one work (14.28%). The rest of the tools used for information extraction were only used in 7.14% of the articles each. This evidence shows a lack of agreement across the scientists constructing these KGs.

The KGs are stored mostly on graph databases such as Neo4j but some are stored on different kinds of databases. For example, one KG was found to be stored in the MongoDB document database, and 2 KG were stored on multipurpose databases such as OrientDB and OpenLink Virtuoso. KGs stored on a Neo4j database can be queried with the cypher query language as it is the default query language. This is the most popular query language for covid-19 KGs, but other languages are also used such as SPARQL endpoint in 14.28% of the KGs. Finally, the format chosen to represent the KGs is only mentioned in 35.72% of the works. However, the most popular formats among these KGs are KGX and GraphML for 14.28% of the KGs. More information should be provided regarding the formats of the KGs in future covid-19 KG works.

The general guidelines presented in this work to construct KGs from scientific literature have been designed in order to be applied for any source of scientific publications. This was achieved by applying and designing the guidelines simultaneously and extracting all the

libraries, sources and methods that were used. However, in order to validate if the guidelines are generalistic, they should be evaluated with users using different sources, methods and libraries to build their KGs, and how they adjust with the guidelines. Moreover, this approach could also help to determine the modularity of the guidelines proposed. Both the modularity and resulting customization possibilities are some of the strengths of our guidelines, so they should be evaluated.

Another benefit of using these guidelines is that not only the desired KG is produced, but also the documents used for its construction are made available with the setup of a document database. This document database contains the structured annotated documents with their corresponding detected entities and if specified, relations between entities. This document database can be explored and more information could be retrieved. As for the KG, it will also be updated through each incremental actualization.

One of the main limitations of our approach is that as of now, some previous knowledge on the methodology is required, as the user needs to interact in all steps of the process. Although this user input may only be the name/URL of the source such as in the first step, other steps require the integration of an API service into the flow. This poses a major difficulty for scientists that currently don't have the capacity to program, and thus limits the reach of these guidelines to experts and other users with some knowledge in API integration. However, for this reason, we implemented the guidelines as an example, so that our implementation could be followed and any part could be reused into the wanted flow.

Another possible weakness of this guide is that it relies on the continuity of the input source. That is, if the input source of publications is taken down, the KG becomes static and will not get updated with the new information. One possibility to overcome this problem, is that this guide could also propose alternative sources to use, or that the user could provide another source to ingest.

From the implementation of the proposed guidelines, several lessons were learnt. Most importantly, the guidelines can be easily implemented in the case of the Drugs4Covid project and the CORD-19 dataset due to the regularity of the actualizations. The generated workflow is almost entirely automatic, and produces a named KG for each actualization containing the new information collected in these publications. The implementation has shown the potential of the high modularity of the guidelines presented, with an easy implementation and customization of each one of the steps. All the desired libraries and resources to be used were implemented without problem.

The main limitation encountered was the execution triggering of the workflow. Ideally, the workflow should be able to detect changes in the source of publications, removing the need for any interaction to run once set up, however, it has not been achieved in this implementation. The execution of the workflow is as of now either manual or scheduled. For it to be scheduled, there needs to be a system that runs the workflow at a given time, dictated by dates given by the user. This could be done through a simple CRON²¹ expression if the system is deployed in a UNIX system, but other strategies need to be sought for this implementation in other operating systems. Another limitation was the

²¹ https://docs.oracle.com/cd/E12058_01/doc/doc.1014/e12030/cron_expressions.htm

detection of the incremental, which requires the download of the full CORD-19 corpus in .tar.gz, and thus is not yet fully optimized but functional nonetheless.

As for more future work, a strategy still needs to be conceived to deal with the publications that are being removed from the source of publications. This removal can have various explanations, one of them is the withdrawal due to inaccuracy of the results, approach or any other potential reason. When the veracity of the findings of a scientific publication is questionable, the information collected from this article should also be withdrawn from the KG. Each step of the implementation could be dockerized in order to increase the modularity of the implementation and allow for a greater customization of the flow. Moreover, the Apache-Nifi workflow will be deployed in a docker container, making it available for the public as an example of an implementation of the guidelines.

6. Conclusions

Thanks to this review work, valuable resources have been identified to continue in this line of research available and the common steps among the methodologies applied to build KGs more efficiently. Moreover, some concerns have been raised about the availability of the resources and reproducibility of the covid-19 KGs. The methodology followed in each article needs to be explained more in detail in order to help other researchers understand and replicate the process used to construct the KG. Furthermore, there does not seem to be a standard methodology common amongst the different works where the methodology was mentioned.

This implementation has shown to be highly customizable due to the modularity of the guidelines proposed. Each step can be customized to use the libraries, models and parsers specified by the user. Moreover, it has potential to work if an event-trigger execution can be defined. For future work lines, a system could be developed with an integrated UI to further help researchers with the construction process.

The implementation of the guidelines presented in this work in the case of the Drugs4Covid project has shown some advantages and limitations. To start, the main limitation of this implementation is that it requires user interaction to start the flow. This is because no service to detect updates in the CORD-19 archive has been set up. In order to circumvent this issue, the flow can be triggered by a CRON expression or an external timer, however this scheduling of the execution does not guarantee the detection of an update to the corpus.

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